

Additional Activity Reporting

Partnership

EOSC: European Partnership for the European Open Science Cloud

Total Amount per Partnership

292162962

Additional Activity category

1. Support to additional R&I

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category covers:

- a) Additional (i.e. not receiving/having received EU funding) R&I funded and executed by private partners in the association;
- b) Additional (i.e. not receiving/having received EU funding) R&I funded by a public research funder (which is a partner in the association, or not) and executed by private partners in the association (n.b. regional or national programmes to support R&I are often offered by public funders).
- c) Additional (i.e. not receiving/having received EU funding) R&I funded by a public research funder which is a partner in the association through for instance a regional or national R&I funding programme.

For case b) above, please note that:

- If a private partner has received co-funding for a project from a public entity which is NOT a partner in the association, then only the part financed by the private partner should be counted in this category (but not the part co-financed by the public entity).

For case c) above, please note that:

- If a private partner has received co-funding for a project from a public entity which IS a partner in the association, then the entire project should be counted in this category (also the part co-financed by the public entity).

R&I should be understood as covering the full range of TRL levels.

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
- No

Amount per category

148 478 941 €

Additional Activity Number

1.1

Additional Activity Name

Upgrade of existing research infrastructures and e-infrastructures so that they may be federated through EOSC

Additional Activity type

1.1 Upgrade of existing research infrastructures and e-infrastructures so that they may be federated through EOSC

Description of Additional Activity

1. Upgrade of institutional and national repositories (e.g., upgrade of the data catalogues)
2. Upgrade of existing institutional, local, and national data infrastructures (e.g., databases, publishing platforms)
3. Implementation of interfaces to integrate computer and data management solutions to ease access and reuse data
4. Scale up the e-infrastructure capabilities of data centres and improving their connectivity with the EOSC and other European infrastructures
5. Upgrade of data storage infrastructures and/ or research data management services (e.g., extension of processing capabilities, extension of data storage capacity, upgrade of DOI management application)
6. Provision of portals and service desks for Open Sciences related tools
7. Provision of tools for secure collaboration between researchers

8. Upgrade of the SSH Open Marketplace
 9. Integration of FAIR-Data services in infrastructure
 10. Integration of a new data processing centre in the EOSC portal, offering Cloud resources to EU researchers and upgrade of existing scientific cloud providers in the EOSC portal

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
 GO2- Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
 GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
 SO4- Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
 SO6- Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
 SO7- EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
 SO8- Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
 OO2- Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)
 OO5- Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
 OO10- Deploy and operate an authentication and OO10 authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024
 OO11- Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025
 OO13- Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

116 405 130 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1.1

Success Story Name

Upgrade Platform: data managing plans - Ghent University

Success story description

Ghent University has been enhancing infrastructure provided to their researchers such as - upgrade the platform for managing data managing plans DMPonline.be. Ghent University started the platform and involved other Belgian partners to form a national platform - upgraded the institutional repository <http://biblio.ugent.be> - connected the UGent CRIS system <http://research.ugent.be> to the institutional repository so information can be exchanged between the two platforms. This enriched information flows to external infrastructures such as the Flemish Information Space FRIS and OpenAIRE, through which information flows to EOSC - upgraded the OA publishing platform to the new software Janeway, <http://openjournals.ugent.be> - analysis and first steps of the development of a data vault - development of the data register, ...

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<http://DMPonline.be>

Additional Activity Number

1.2

Additional Activity Name

Development and deployment of EOSC-compatible search engines to allow the researchers to explore rich metadata and semantic descriptions in EOSC-connected registers

Additional Activity type

1.2 Development and deployment of EOSC-compatible search engines to allow the researchers to explore rich metadata and semantic descriptions in EOSC-connected registers

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities type includes as follows:

1. Development of terminology services for exploring, publishing, and developing shared ontologies, vocabularies, and terminologies.
2. Upgrade of catalogues with information about policies for OA, licenses, publication fees and conditions offered by the different institutions
3. Implementation of data catalogues together with an automatic metadata enrichment
4. Development, maintenance, and support of research output discovery in e.g. Limo Lirias, Research Data Repository front-end, metadata distribution to FRIS portal, OpenAire, Google Scholar and Google Dataset Search
5. Development and maintenance of metadata repositories and semantic interoperability tools
6. Upgrade of data catalogues to support data onboarding to thematic and EOSC Data Portals
7. Improvement of standard compliance in all national archives to ensure optimal interoperability through automated testing of metadata quality
8. Implementation of discovery services
9. Integration of existing data repositories with EUDAT services for metadata indexing
10. Maintenance and operation of the PID Central Registry
11. Development of an online platform to reduce the barriers for accessing scientific publications by citizens
12. Establishment of the EOSC-compatible search portal that constitutes a single-entry point for searching, discovery and recall of thousands of scientific and scholarly publications, namely journal articles, conference papers, thesis, and dissertations, distributed by several repositories.
13. Development of the Comprehensive Information System for acquiring, processing, preservation and provision research and bibliometric information and publications
14. Integration of metadata search engine and platform for FAIR epidemiological computational modelling and simulation
15. Instalment and maintenance of infrastructure related to ontology service
16. Preparation of platforms for academic libraries, including search engine for both documents and data from one access point
17. Development and implementation of standards and data interfaces for research information
18. Development and integration of open research knowledge graphs for semantically describing research contributions

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
 SO4- Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
 SO6- Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
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Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

3 478 976 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1.2

Success Story Name

Development and improvement of search functionality - University of Zagreb Computing Centre

Success story description

Development and improvement of search functionality of the national repository infrastructure Digital academic archives and repositories - DABAR (<https://dabar.srce.hr>). With the improvements, all contents and repositories in DABAR are aligned with the current OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repository Managers v4 and OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives. It involved training of repository managers on how to register OpenAIRE interface and it had an impact on all institutional and thematic that are established on DABAR. At the end of 2022 DABAR infrastructure contained 155 digital repositories with 215.678 published digital objects. The activity was performed during the whole of 2022.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

https://dabar.srce.hr

Additional Activity Number

1.3

Additional Activity Name

Deploying EOSC-Core components for FAIR (e.g. the deployment of online tools for data FAIRification or to help creating FAIR Data Management Plans)

Additional Activity type

1.3 Deploying EOSC-Core components for FAIR (e.g. the deployment of online tools for data FAIRification or to help creating FAIR Data Management Plans)

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Development, hosting, maintenance, and support for different FAIR tools to support researchers in every step of the life cycle e.g., DMP tool, PRET platform, iRODS infrastructure for active data management, diversified storage solutions
2. Development and pilot of public data repository services for institutions not having capacity to deploy their own repository
3. Provision of standard services for Data Management Plan Tools and REST API (e.g., DMPOnline)
4. Integration of online DMP tool with organisational tools such as repositories and data registers
5. Establishment and implementation of machine-actionable DMP tools
6. Integration of local CRIS systems with DMP tool
7. Development of DMPonline Metadata for Machines toolbox for ontologies and metadata definition
8. Upgrade of Data Management Expert Guides and realisation of Data Archiving Guides for data experts
9. Implementation of DMP standards
10. Collaboration on FAIR DMPs, collaboration on Data Stewardship Wizard deployment
11. Enhancement of existing UIs for data access in correspondence with EOSC requirements for FAIR data
12. Development and deployment of Domain Data Protocols and F-UJI FAIR assessment tools
13. Contribution to various FAIR-related initiatives, which analyse research systems and experiments with new tools and approaches to science funding
14. Development of Paediatric Data interoperability service where users can access tools for identifying, accessing, integrating, and analysing paediatric data to facilitate sharing and re-use of data according to the FAIR principles
15. Deployment of online tools to support the creation of Data Management Plans (DMPs)
16. Deployment of management platforms for metadata quality
17. Implementation of FAIR data in existing repositories
18. Establishment of the FAIR Checker - a tool to assess the FAIR metrics of a resource

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
 GO2- Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
 GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
 SO6- Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
 OO5- Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

12 193 719 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1.3

Success Story Name

Data management expert guide - Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

Success story description

Upgrade of the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide and the CESSDA Website. It also includes outreach and branding of this DMEG. Realisation of the Data Archiving Guide (DAG) for data experts.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://www.cessda.eu>

Additional Activity Number

1.4

Additional Activity Name

Development and publication of large scale studies

Additional Activity type

1.4 Development and publication of large scale studies

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Funding of two large cohort studies: the Swiss Transplant and the HIV Cohort Study
2. Large-scale studies under the project IDE@S (Innovative Data Environment @ Styria) that aims to foster the cooperation between industry and HEIs in data science
3. Policy regulations for the sharing of research data, a study of strategies and regulations
4. Mapping and analysis of Open Science policy developments at international, European, and national level

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
 GO2-Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
 SO5- The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
 SO6- Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
 SO8- Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
 OO1- Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
 OO2- Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

2 753 000 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1.4

Success Story Name

Collaborative use of research data - Graz University of Technology

Success story description

Large-scale studies are planned to be conducted in the project IDE@S (Innovative Data Environment @ Styria). IDE@S is a cooperative project between four Styrian higher education institutions (HEIs) - TU Graz, Karl-Franzens Universität Graz, Medizinische Universität Graz and FH Joanneum - funded by the Government of Styria aiming to develop a regional reference model for the collaborative use of research data. This will foster the cooperation between industry and HEIs in data science, thus strengthening Styria's research and industry position and increasing its visibility throughout Europe. The current study results have been published:
<https://doi.org/10.3390/data7020020>

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://doi.org/10.3390/data7020020>

Additional Activity Number **Additional Activity Name**
1.5 Contribution to operating core functions of a Minimum Viable EOSC ecosystem

Additional Activity type

1.5 Contribution to operating core functions of a Minimum Viable EOSC ecosystem

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Maintenance, improvement, and operation of services for cloud orchestration related to the EOSC EGI Cloud Compute
2. Implementation of MVE Research Infrastructures (e.g. Connectome Research Infrastructure)
3. Exploitation of AAI Federation and access to Géant EduGain
4. Development of the Persistent Identification (PID) service
5. Development of the Research Activity Identifier that helps identify not only research projects but also identify infrastructure used in research projects
7. AAI infrastructure development and maintenance of AAI federation in platforms (e.g. ELIXIR, B2ACCES)
8. Maintenance of provider profiles on the EOSC Portal
9. Integration of generic data science platform in the EOSC portal, with links to existing EOSC-Exchange services, according to EOSC specifications and architecture
10. New generation platform for libraries, WG Metadata schemas, National Metadata Catalogue, National Centre for PIDs

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2-Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO5- The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
SO6- Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
SO7- EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
SO8- Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
OO1- Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
OO5- Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
OO10- Deploy and operate an authentication and OO10 authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024
OO11- Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

13 648 116 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1.5

Success Story Name

E-infrastructure enabling Open Science practices & Identifiers for FAIR Research Information - Coöperatie SURF u.a.

Success story description

Name of the initiative/action: e-infrastructure enabling Open Science practices. PID service and AAI (SRAM). - primary purpose: The assignment of ePIC is to set up and maintain a reliable joint service for registering, storing and resolving persistent identifiers based on handles for the research community. AAI (SRAM) providing research collaborations with easy and secure access to research services. - which communities or stakeholders are involved: ePIC (CLARIN, CNC, CSC, CSCS, DKRZ, grnet, GWDG, SND, SURF), AAI/SRAM (SURF). - which communities or stakeholders are addressed (e.g. discipline clusters); national infrastructures and scientific communities, European projects and infrastructures. - whether mono or multidisciplinary: multidisciplinary - expected outcome and impact; ePIC (sustainable registering and identifying research) objects, AAI (SRAM) (enable the collaboration of researchers) - implementation and/or impact timeline: ongoing. - WEBPAGE address: <https://www.pidconsortium.net/> <https://www.surf.nl/en/surf-research-access-management-easy-and-secure-access-to-research-services>

Name of the initiative/action: Identifiers for FAIR Research Information - primary purpose: Build a broader understanding of the international PID landscape and create broader awareness of the current and future possibilities of PID applications and ensure that information about research will be more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. - which communities or stakeholders are involved: pid service providers and research performing organisations - which communities or stakeholders are addressed (e.g. discipline clusters); research funding, - performing and service provisioning organisations. - whether mono or multidisciplinary: multidisciplinary - expected outcome and impact; - implementation and/or impact timeline: a roadmap for further activities. - WEBPAGE address: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5836056>

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5836056>

Additional Activity category

2. Scale-up of technologies

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category covers different scale-up activities (typically at TRL levels 4-5) . These are mostly trials/tests of proof of concept models, i.e. validation of the technology in lab or relevant environment. These activities must be totally funded and executed by private partners only. If there is public co-funding, they should be reported in Category 1.

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
 No

Amount per category

11 625 605 €

Additional Activity Number

2.1

Additional Activity Name

Investment done complementing the results of a project, bringing it to a higher TRL level (e.g. EOSC thematic services) or to deployment

Additional Activity type

2.1 - Investment done complementing the results of a project, bringing it to a higher TRL level (e.g. EOSC thematic services) or to deployment

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

- 1.Continuous improvement of services registered in EOSC Portal
- 2.Metrics service deployment
- 3.Support on the development of EOSC thematic services for the development of a Medical Imaging Real World Data repository to create a biobank on medical imaging data, internally funded by the institution
- 4.Sustaining outcomes of the SSHOC cluster project to become TRL-8 services.

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2-Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO4- Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO7- EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
SO8- Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
OO1- Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
OO5- Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

530 000 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

2.1

Success Story Name

EOSC thematic services - Universitat Politècnica de València

Success story description

Support on the development of EOSC thematic services for the development of a Medical Imaging Real World Data repository to create a biobank on medical imaging data, internally funded by the institution. The data will be made available openly but considering ethical and legal constraints. _x000D_ Both activities will leverage services from the EOSC marketplace.

Audience or target group

Website

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Additional Activity Number

2.2

Additional Activity Name

Uptake of EOSC projects' outcomes through adoption of, for instance, new open specifications, standards for data interoperability, common EOSC frameworks for managing AAI, also but not exclusively in the context of public procurements

Additional Activity type

2.2 Uptake of EOSC projects' outcomes through adoption of, for instance, new open specifications, standards for data interoperability, common EOSC frameworks for managing AAI, also but not exclusively in the context of public procurements

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. The investment in the SSH Open Marketplace will be maintained as part of the post-project sustainability plan for continued collaboration by the RIs in SSH
2. Exploitation of EOSC services for a Satellite Image Processing Thematic service
3. Adoption of outcomes of relevant projects (e.g. SSHOC, EOSC Future, OpenAIRE, OPERAS)
4. Injection of knowledge from 'EOSC interoperability framework' and 'A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)' and AAI architecture into national working groups and upcoming projects
5. Development and implementation of standards and data interfaces for research information (Subproject 1), Concept Study for a Research Portal (Subproject 2)
6. Development Interfaces for shared research infrastructures
7. Adoption of repositories (Data Stations) and LTP-systems (vault) to fit into EOSC frameworks
8. Implementation of AAI into institution online services, using EOSC compute services in scientific pipelines
9. Development of guidelines on adoption of standards for interoperability in institutional and national settings
10. FBI data roadmap for 2022: using the EOSC standards and AAI for biological image management

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2- Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO4- Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO5- The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
SO7- EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
OO1- Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
OO5- Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
OO6- Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership
OO10- Deploy and operate an authentication and OO10 authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024
OO11- Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025
OO12- Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

1 150 000 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

2.2

Success Story Name

Guidelines and standards for interoperability- OpenAIRE

Success story description

Guiding our members on how to adopt guidelines and standards for interoperability in institutional and national settings. This includes guidelines for repositories and for monitoring of open science.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website**Additional Activity Number**

2.3

Additional Activity Name

Implementation of technical specifications required to provide services through the EOSC

Additional Activity type

2.3 Implementation of technical specifications required to provide services through the EOSC

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Standardization and vocabulary development activities relevant for EOSC
2. Implementation of state-of-the-art standards for metadata, interoperability and persistent identification for the upgrading of the cultural heritage digitised collections repository
3. Adoption of service templates at all service provider archives
4. Implementation of technical specifications required to provide repository and LTP services through the EOSC
5. Support implementation interoperability guidelines
6. Support repository platforms to embed functionalities for specs

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
 GO2- Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
 GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
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 SO5- The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
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 OO6- Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership
 OO10- Deploy and operate an authentication and OO10 authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024
 OO11- Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025
 OO12- Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

9 836 719 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

2.3

Success Story Name

Implementation of standards for metadata, interoperability and persistent identification - Alma MaTTER

Success story description

Implementation of state of the art standards for metadata, interoperability and persistent identification for the upgrading of the cultural heritage digitised collections repository (AMSHIstorica).

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website<http://amsacta.unibo.it>**Additional Activity category**

3. Demonstrators

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category covers demonstrations of a prototype. These demonstration activities would typically be at TRL levels 6-8. These activities must be totally funded and executed by private partners only. If there is public-co-funding, they should be reported in Category 1.

Additional activity reported under this category

Yes
 No

Amount per category

21 540 346 €

Additional Activity Number

3.1

Additional Activity Name

Investment in new platforms, demonstrators, pilot use cases exploiting domain-specific user environments and supporting the EOSC vision including the value of sharing FAIR and open research data and other research digital objects such as software

Additional Activity type

3.1 Investment in new platforms, demonstrators, pilot use cases exploiting domain-specific user environments and supporting the EOSC vision including the value of sharing FAIR and open research data and other research digital objects such as software

Description of Additional Activity

his Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Pilot new services and applications in the context of the Open Research Knowledge Graph for various science domains
2. Update of the Digital Object Gateway demonstrator
3. Development of the AlmaHealthDB infrastructure, adopting a FAIR by design approach, and develop a shared infrastructure for ensuring the highest interoperability level
4. Build a repository for Medical Image data in Cancer for research, applying FAIR principles
5. Investments concerning the further development of a MVP Discovery Platform and use-case development to uptake features developed on top of the Connectome Knowledge Graph (future interoperable with EOSC)
6. In kind contribution of BBMRI-ERIC members and employees for the development of the federated data platform
7. Labs Digital Data Exchange Project piloting data sharing and data sovereignty options, lead to potential new services
8. Build technical prototypes in EOSC-compatible frameworks, showcase them and work with end-users
9. Set up vocabulary registries as a demonstrator for a federated registry service infrastructure
10. Development of prototype of a flexible science platform for the access of open astroparticle data available through the EOSC
11. Development & implementation of standards & data interfaces for research information
12. Data storage system connected to the university Cloud & HPC services, systematically requiring a DMP, to prepare a simple/smooth transition to an EOSC repository to open the data
13. Development of domain-specific computational environment built on JupyterHub/Binder
14. Analysis of EOSC requirements on complex workflow orchestration and distributed data management and their integration to the LEXIS platform
15. Development of a new platform devoted to Health Data

16. Establishment/provision of funding for new data centres.
17. Coordination, curation, and hosting of Covid-19 national platforms
18. Development of an IT platform for repurposing medicines focused on paediatric diseases, based on an innovative model including a fit-for-purpose IT environment for dedicated data analytics
19. Dataverse infrastructure for FAIR geospatial data including contributing to the community metadata standards
20. Upscaling of IPCC-Atlas Hub, integration with EOSC authentication system & EOSC Exchange
21. Investment in collaboration with ICT consortia on how to use the OpenAIRE Graph
22. Build a core component of national research and innovation e-infrastructures with long-term advanced computing and storage resources and network connectivity
23. Provision of services & infrastructures for data management and High-Performance Computing (replicated massive data storage, cloud infrastructures, computing and visualisation nodes)
24. Development of PC oriented computing infrastructure, Big Data computing infrastructure and infrastructure for on-demand cloud services that jointly offer secure data storage, scientific computing on the cloud, software, virtual machines, collaborative research, and computing facilities equipped with technical support and setup for user access
25. Development/running Data Repository services allowing the publication of large-scale datasets to support researchers to make large data sets FAIR and discoverable within EOSC
26. Development of advanced data management and analysis capabilities linked to strategic Supercomputing infrastructures
27. Development of a national platform for the implementation of EOSC

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
- GO2- Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
- GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
- SO4- Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
- SO5- The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
- SO6- Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
- SO7- EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
- SO8- Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
- OO1- Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
- OO4- Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO5- Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
- OO6- Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO12- Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
- No

Funding sources

- Public
- Private

Amount per activity

21 440 346 €

Success story

- Yes
- No

Success story number

3.1

Success Story Name

New Health Data Platform - Université de Montpellier

Success story description

The Montpellier Data Science Institute and Meso@LR have invested in a new platform devoted to Health Data on the basis of a collaboration with Inserm. Meso@LR provides services and infrastructures for data management and High Performance Computing: replicated massive data storage, Health data, Cloud infrastructures, computing and visualisation nodes, including big memory nodes, etc.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia

Website

Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Additional Activity Number

3.2

Additional Activity Name

New (pre-)commercial services and capabilities along the data life cycle addressing current and anticipated needs of the research community at large

Additional Activity type

3.2 New (pre-)commercial services and capabilities along the data life cycle addressing current and anticipated needs of the research community at large

Description of Additional Activity

1. Definition of services and related policies for data management, processing and orchestration in accordance with potential commercial use-cases
2. Implementation of the EOSC AAI within EuroHPC

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2- Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO7 EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
OO1 Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
OO5 Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
OO10 Deploy and operate an authentication and OO10 authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

100 000 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

3.2

Success Story Name

Definition of services and related policies - VSB (Technical University of Ostrava)

Success story description

Definition of services and related policies for data management, processing and orchestration in accordance with potential commercial use-cases.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

Additional Activity category

4. Creating new business opportunities

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category includes activities which aim at turning a fully developed and functional innovation into a business opportunity. It concerns activities such as investing in start-ups, spin-offs, incubators, accelerators etc. that will take forward the solutions/products developed within the partnership's projects. Please note that "Creating business opportunities" can only happen once the product or service is available in its fully developed form (i.e. when the "Scale-up of technologies" step is

fully finished, and normally also when the "Demonstrators" step has been finished).

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
 No

Amount per category

646 350 €

Additional Activity Number	Additional Activity Name	
4.1	Invest in start-ups, spin-offs on solutions developed within the projects	
Additional Activity type		
4.1 Invest in start-ups, spin-offs on solutions developed within the projects		
Description of Additional Activity		
This Additional Activities' type includes as follows: 1. Support the creation of spinoffs by universities with a 5% stake 2. Transfer of BSC engineering applications to new spin-offs		
Link to partnership general objectives		
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results		
Link to partnership specific objectives		
SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)		
Link to projects	Funding sources	Amount per activity
<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Private	136 000 €
Success story		
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No		

Success story number	
4.1	
Success Story Name	
Spinoffs - University of Vigo	
Success story description	
The University of Vigo supports the creation of spinoffs with a 5% stake. It also promotes calls to provide workspaces within the university campus to recently created spinoffs. On the other hand, it works with the university community to help them foster their entrepreneurial skills and enter the job market, acquiring the ability to create jobs and not just look for them, through the INCUVI program. This program aims to support entrepreneurial ideas and accelerate and consolidate viable entrepreneurial projects promoted by students or recent graduates.	
Audience or target group	Website
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research Institutes <input type="checkbox"/> Public at large	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Academia <input type="checkbox"/> Public Authorities <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other
	https://www.uvigo.gal/es/estudiar/empleabilidad/quieres-emprender/programacion-incuvi

Additional Activity Number	Additional Activity Name
4.2	Start incubators/accelerators
Additional Activity type	
4.2 Start incubators/accelerators	
Description of Additional Activity	
This Additional Activities' type includes as follows: 1. Organisation of bootcamps, hackathons and datathons 2. Support the creation and development of innovative start-ups with high technological intensity and growth potential, founded both by university researchers and students, and by external entrepreneurs, providing strategic consulting services, coaching, mentoring, fundraising support, and spaces 3. SWITCH Innovation Labs concerning the harnessing of Open Science with a focus one Open Research Data - Budget Labs	

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

289 350 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

4.2

Success Story Name

Start-ups - Politecnico di Torino

Success story description

I3P supports the creation and development of innovative start-ups with high technological intensity and growth potential, founded both by university researchers and students, and by external entrepreneurs, providing strategic consulting services, coaching, mentoring, fundraising support and spaces. The Incubator of the Polytechnic of Turin I3P is the Best Public Business Incubator in the world as recognized by the World Rankings of Business Incubators and Accelerators 2019-2020. The ranking is drawn up by UBI Global, the most important international organisation active in the benchmarking of incubation and acceleration programmes linked to university institutions.

Audience or target group

- Industry
 Research Institutes
 Public at large
 Academia
 Public Authorities
 Other

Website

<https://www.i3p.it/en/>

Additional Activity Number

4.3

Additional Activity Name

Matchmaking between different start-ups, - SMEs, participating companies, stakeholders

Additional Activity type

4.3 Matchmaking between different start-ups, - SMEs, participating companies, stakeholders

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Organisation of workshops with representatives of non-academic partners to develop a more articulate overview of existing opportunities and conditions for service provision and collaboration (innovation based on co-development)
2. Organisation of info days and matchmaking events
3. Support for SMEs to deliver new innovative products via the EOSC Future DIH

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

121 000 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

4.3

Success Story Name

Innovation based on co-development - Clarin-Eric

Success story description

In 2022 workshops are planned with representatives of non-academic partners in order to develop a more articulate overview of existing opportunities and conditions for service provision and collaboration (innovation based on co-development).

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-workshops>

Additional Activity Number

4.4

Additional Activity Name

Investments in procurement of innovative solutions

Additional Activity type

4.4 Investments in procurement of innovative solutions

Description of Additional Activity

1. Procurement of innovative platform for scientific data preservation and management

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)

OO7 Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan-European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

100 000 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Additional Activity category

5. Training and skills development

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category covers activities that aim to identify and perform the skills and training programmes needed for the workforce that will produce and/or use the new product/service.

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
 No

Amount per category

26 343 700 €

Additional Activity Number

5.1

Additional Activity Name

Addressing the development of education, training and skills development in Open science and FAIR data management of research artefacts.

Additional Activity type

5.1 Addressing the development of education, training and skills development in Open science and FAIR data management of research artefacts. Coordinating and aligning relevant curricula on skills for FAIR and Open Science, and training frameworks for young researchers, civil servants and policy makers

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Various education, training, and skills development activities (such as webinars, video recordings and screencasts) in Open science and FAIR data management of research artefacts also in the context of EOSC related services
2. Contribution to the National Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition
3. Support to RPOs in delivering training on FAIR and RDM
4. Development of training materials and courses covering RDM topics like anonymization, best practices, FAIR principles
5. Data stewards' recruitment campaigns
6. Trainings on Data Management Plan and data archiving provided by data repository staff to researchers involved in funded projects
7. RDM support desks and OS support desks
8. Training on ISO standards on data quality, security and on information transfer systems
9. Development of data stewardship curriculums, establishment of data steward training programmes, data stewardship certificate courses
10. Development of training resources about Open Science and FAIR data for the arts and humanities research communities
11. Annual course on Responsible Research and Innovation with a specific stress on OS and FAIR
12. Involvement in various working groups on FAIR data, data management
13. Advisory services, courses and OS trainings for students, PhD candidates, university authorities, administrative staff, librarians
14. Metadata for Machines workshops
15. +B57 Training activities focusing on experts (train-the-trainers) and researchers (data producers and data users)
16. Diploma for 'scientific data management', certifications in Open Science
17. Development of leadership programmes to foster the right policy environment that supports digital skills and training at institutional and national level
18. Build capacities to sustain learning corpora for digital skills and tools so that EOSC represents a trusted and long-lasting knowledge hub
19. Cycle of conferences within the framework of the HRS4R to promote scientific careers, incorporating aspects related to open science, FAIR data management plan
20. Training platforms with courses on Open Access publishing and FAIR data /RDM
21. Continuous upgrading of training materials on FAIR data, RDM, DMP, OA, OS
22. Dedicated activities within Open Science Competence Centres and Knowledge Research Education Centres
23. Training and dissemination activities among the national RIs connected to ESFRI

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO2 Professional data stewards are increasingly available in research performing organisations in Europe to support Open Science
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO6 Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
OO6 Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

26 343 700 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

5.1

Success Story Name

Training researchers - Gdańsk University of Technology

Success story description

Activities of the Open Science Competence Center at the Library of the Gdańsk University of Technology - improving the qualifications of employees, academic staff, PhD students, and Librarians. The main goal of Open Science Competence Center created in the framework of the MOST DANYCH project at Gdańsk Tech Library is to offer guidance and support to researchers about publishing in an open access, preparing Data Management Plan and making data accessible in the research data repository. The Center offers various trainings, consultancies, and other events promoting the idea of opening science. Publishing open research offers a number

of benefits: • increased citation and usage • greater public engagement • wider collaboration • faster impact • increased interdisciplinary conversation • compliance with open access mandates.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

https://pg.edu.pl/en/openscience/about-us

Additional Activity category

6. Contribution to the development of new standards, regulations and policies

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category includes activities that aim at the development of new standards and regulations and new public policy in the area of the new product/innovation and that will help in entering the innovation into the market and/or enhance its societal uptake.

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
 No

Amount per category

28 011 358 €

Additional Activity Number

6.1

Additional Activity Name

Standardisation and certification activities related to EOSC trusted repositories

Additional Activity type

6.1 Standardisation and certification activities related to EOSC trusted repositories (e.g. CoreTrustSeal and FAIR)

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Preparation of repositories and national repository platform for CTS certification
2. Certification (CoreTrustSeal) of institutional research data repositories
3. Development of FAIR practices, semantics interoperability of FAIR research resources and repositories
4. Support for CoreTrustSeal certification
5. Extension of activities of Meta Data Offices, including the management of meta data profiles
6. Preparation of certification documentation for the Sensitive Cloud to deal with sensitive (health-related) data
7. Financial contribution to the board and secretariat of Core Trust Seal
8. Operation of internal ORD working groups
9. Operation of the Metadata Validator services
10. Contribution to national Computing and Data Infrastructure activities
11. Investment in repository certifications stimulate the awareness and skill-levels for how to make data FAIR and help increase the volume of FAIR language data collections
12. Provision of funds for participation of data providers to develop standards for interoperability
13. Application of FAIR principles and Core Trust Seal certification (RDA & WDS) for Data Centers and services of the Ocean and Solid Earth
14. Maintenance of certification services related to Core Trust Seal

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO6 Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
OO6 Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership
OO12 Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

1 578 178 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

6.1

Success Story Name

Trusted repositories - National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS)

Success story description

ASOV organization of meetings with french data centers and data providers to explain how to become trusted repositories.// The CDS is maintaining (or implementing) the certification of its services by CoreTrustSeal.//Data Terra RI ODATIS Ocean and ForM@Ter Solid Earth Data Hub : Application of FAIR principles and Core Trust Seal certification (RDA & WDS) for Data Centers and services of the Ocean and Solid Earth data center (ANR Flash : Copilote and CEDRE)
ASOV funds participation of french data providers to develop standards for interoperability. Some of them are tested in EOSC context_x000D_ Data Terra RI : guideline for FAIR principle applications (DMP, Licenses, interoperability standards, Authentication, Catalogs)"

Audience or target group

Website

Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Additional Activity Number

6.2

Additional Activity Name

Translate FAIR guidelines and frameworks to make them applicable to other digital objects, such as software, code, data management plans, protocols

Additional Activity type

6.2 Translate FAIR guidelines and frameworks to make them applicable to other digital objects, such as software, code, data management plans, protocols

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Templates, protocols, and guidelines to manage data according to FAIR principles for the research community, provided by Data Stewards
2. Software development of data analysis under open code principles to guarantee its future reusability and data provenance
3. Contribution to the development of applicable FAIR guidelines and DMP elaboration guidelines
4. Development of FAIR practices, semantics interoperability of FAIR research resources and repositories
5. Upgrade the pISA-tree framework for FAIR data management of life science projects
6. Preparation of FAIR guidelines for research projects
7. Support different research communities in practical solutions to make their infrastructure and procedures FAIR engage in development of template DMPs
8. Development of Metadata for Machines tools
9. Participation in activities related to national Minimal DMPs
10. Contribution to the European Software Sustainability Initiative (EUSSI), the Workshops on Sustainable Software Sustainability (WOSSS) and the FAIR Software Route
11. Contribution to the development of institutional and national guidelines for RDM
12. Participation to RDA, IVOA, IHDEA, IPDA working groups
13. Involvement in EOSC Association's Task Forces work
14. Development and upgrade of guidelines for publications, data, software, other research products
15. Implementation of discipline specific RDM strategies
16. Guidelines for FAIR applications (DMP, Licenses, interoperability standards, Authentication, Catalogues)

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO2 Professional data stewards are increasingly available in research performing organisations in Europe to support Open Science
SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO5 The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
OO3 Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership
OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
OO5 Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)

OO6 Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership

OO7 Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan- European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025

OO8 Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

6 719 611 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

6.2

Success Story Name

Policy and Guidelines - Uppsala University

Success story description

Drafting local Data Management policy and guidelines. Work performed within the Data Office but also in collaboration with other Swedish Universities.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

Additional Activity Number

6.3

Additional Activity Name

Continuous standardisation of PID resource types and promotion of new practices to expand the range of identifiable research objects

Additional Activity type

6.3 Continuous standardisation of PID resource types and promotion of new practices to expand the range of identifiable research objects e.g. instruments, services, organisations and software

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

- 1.Collaboration with Data Cite on various PID standardization activities
- 2.Implementation of a PID identifier (provided by DataCite) in the raw data of sets collected in different experimental stations
- 3.Application in institutional context (eRA, PID service), contributions to committees (e.g., DataCite, CrossRef, ORCID-DE, Eurocris)
- 4.Work with DataCite DOI service
- 5.Establishment of national PID roadmaps
- 6.Integration of ORCID, DOI and other PID in university system
- 7.PID management, nation-wide services DOI-Service, ORCID, activities in the RDA National PID Strategies Working Group
- 8.Alignment of PID usage across national DOI users
- 9.Involvement in EOSC Association's Task Forces work (EOSC Task Force PID policy and implementation)
- 10.Collaboration on national PID infrastructures for FAIR data
- 11.Contribution to various national and international PID standardisation activities
- 12.Contribution to the PID Architecture and design document
- 13.Costs related to PIDs licencing (DataCite, Handle, CrossRef, ORCID).
- 14.Operation of the OpenOrgs service that bridges identifiers of organisations from different registries
- 15.Using and promoting the use of DOI for OGS digital materials
- 16.Establishment of National Centres for PIDs (ISSN, ORCID consortium, DataCite consortium, ROR)

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO2 Professional data stewards are increasingly available in research performing organisations in Europe to support Open Science

SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science

SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design

SO5 The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts

OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
 OO7 Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan- European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025
 OO8 Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership
 OO11 Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

5 906 000 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

6.3

Success Story Name

PID - Coöperatie SURF u.a.

Success story description

Name of the initiative/action: National roadmap for persistent identifiers - primary purpose: To counteract the fragmentation of identifiers in the global landscape of research information, the demand for a national roadmap for PIDs has arisen. - which communities or stakeholders are involved: UKB, NWO, KNAW DANS, Leiden University/CWTS, UU, eScience Center and 4TU.ResearchData. SURF - which communities or stakeholders are addressed (e.g. discipline clusters); funding organisations, research performing organizations, publishers, research service organisations. - whether mono or multidisciplinary: multidisciplinary - expected outcome and impact; The roadmap and PID use cases is intended as an instrument to strengthen the coherence of stakeholder developments and to increase the impact through the use of PIDs. - implementation and/or impact timeline: 2022-2023. - WEBPAGE address: <https://www.surf.nl/en/national-roadmap-for-persistent-identifiers>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5849310>

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5849310>

Additional Activity Number

6.4

Additional Activity Name

Support all research communities to develop and adopt domain-specific standards and to consolidate common metadata and data schemata for use in the EOSC context

Additional Activity type

6.4 Support all research communities to develop and adopt domain-specific standards and to consolidate common metadata and data schemata for use in the EOSC context

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Support domain specific development of ontologies for semantic web applications
2. Support to LifeWatch and CSIC's Teledetection Thematic Platform on the adoption of relevant standards for their domains of knowledge and FAIR principles
3. Support to the implementation of data standards
4. Development of Flemish Standard for Research Data
5. Support arts and humanities research communities in developing/adopting new standards and policies,
6. Participation in the following EOSC-Association task forces: TF Upskilling Countries to Engage in EOSC, TF Research Careers, Recognition, and Credit, TF Defining Funding Models for EOSC and TF Semantic interoperability
7. Contribution to FOSB working group architecture - use cases
8. Support for adopting metadata and file format standards to ease data access and discovery
9. Development of national open science plans, development, and promotion of institutional OS policies
10. Support for several research communities in standardisation by data steward teams
11. Activities in the GEO Data Working Group
12. Support research communities (e.g., migration, historical financial data, religious studies, election studies) to implement dedicated metadata
13. Support research communities, mainly in the SSH, to adopt domain-specific standards
14. Development of Code of Conduct for Health Research
15. Preparation for National Metadata Catalogues for research data

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
 GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find,

access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research

SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design

OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership

OO5 Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)

OO12 Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025

Link to projects

Yes

No

Funding sources

Public

Private

Amount per activity

13 807 569 €

Success story

Yes

No

Success story number

6.4

Success Story Name

Metadata standards - National Library of Technology

Success story description

Leading the national WG for metadata standards for research data + preparation for national project CARDS where one of the activities is focused on common metadata schema and metadata interoperability.

Audience or target group

Website

Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Additional Activity category

7. Supporting ecosystem development

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category includes activities that aim at further developing and integrating the R&I ecosystem in the partnership's area - for example, knowledge sharing with technology clusters, innovation hubs, networking structures and other R&I bodies, cross-partnership cooperation.

Additional activity reported under this category

Yes

No

Amount per category

33 473 995 €

Additional Activity Number

7.1

Additional Activity Name

Define and test financing models for a lasting long-term EOSC sustainability framework

Additional Activity type

7.1 Define and test financing models for a lasting long-term EOSC sustainability framework

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

- 1.Co-definition of a sustainability framework with the members of the Hellenic Open Science Initiative
- 2.Participation in EOSC-A Task Force 'Long term data preservation'
- 3.Contribution to the work of EOSC Association Financial Sustainability Task Force development of national models for financial sustainability
- 4.Establishment of working group for defining and assessing business models for OpenAIRE services
- 5.Build ICDI Legal Entity: management effort, legal expenses, initial capital for all members

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

OO13 Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users
OO14 Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

339 800 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

7.1

Success Story Name

Legal Entity Built - Consortium GARR Association (Gestione Ampliamento Rete Ricerca)

Success story description

Building ICDI Legal Entity: management effort, legal expenses, initial capital for all members – from next year fees and capital will be accounted for in ICDI LE's monitoring]

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

Additional Activity Number

7.2

Additional Activity Name

Development of consensual EOSC frameworks and guidelines

Additional Activity type

7.2 Development of consensual EOSC frameworks and guidelines (e.g. for interoperability, AAI, the implementation of EOSC rules of participation)

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

- 1.Participating in EOSC-A Advisory Group 'Technical challenges on EOSC' – Task Force 'AAI Architecture', Task Force 'Technical interoperability of data and services'
- 2.Participation in EOSC Rules of Participation Compliance Monitoring working group
- 3.Work on EOSC compatible AAI ecosystem for specific scientific domains (primary Life Science and Healthcare)
- 4.Contribution to AAI standards and best practices definition from the HPC centre and related services operator perspective
- 5.Participation in the definition of SRIA and the corresponding Architecture, AAI
- 6.Participation in the EOSC Association's Task Forces: Rules of Participation Compliance Monitoring, Long-Term Data Preservation

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO5 The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
OO5 Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
OO13 Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public

Amount per activity

547 000 €

Private

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

7.2

Success Story Name

Task Forces - European Organization for Nuclear Research

Success story description

CERN personnel are members of the EOSC Association's task forces: Rules of Participation, Compliance Monitoring, Long-Term Data Preservation, Technical Interoperability of Data and Services

Audience or target group

Website

Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Additional Activity Number

7.3

Additional Activity Name

Support to knowledge building and sharing with the research domains to support data-intensive-science and inter-disciplinary research

Additional Activity type

7.3 Support to knowledge building and sharing with the research domains to support data-intensive-science and inter-disciplinary research

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Collaboration with national RPOs and researcher networks
2. Support the publication in Open Science Journals through internal grants
3. Fostering best practices in open science across researchers
4. Dedicated staff to support researchers with interdisciplinary data interoperability across department and projects
5. Establishment of Digital Competence Centers with a focus on improving research data management practises and the adoption of FAIR and Open Science
6. Engagement in several working groups and workshops, e.g., on metrics, architecture, metadata standards
7. Facilitation of dialog across research domains with relevant stakeholders
8. Support all research teams covering the entire data cycle, from writing DMPs, adopting appropriate storage solutions, depositing their datasets in open repositories
9. Communication and dissemination activities towards engagement of research communities in open science practice
10. Collection of regional competences and knowledge and make them available for industry
11. Organisation of a multi-disciplinary, annual scientific and technical users' conferences
12. The cost of personnel in Research Data/ Research Data Management Offices
13. The cost of personnel (developers, system managers, data curators) involved in local research infrastructure work

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
OO2 Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)
OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

8 028 216 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

7.3

Success Story Name

Hub - Fonds Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek Vlaanderen (Research Foundation Flanders)

Success story description

Coordination of the Flemish Open Science Board (FOSB) and the Flemish Research Data Network (FRDN), a forum c.q. network for the development of a uniform and concerted OS policy for Flemish universities and research institutions. Their coordination hub is situated at FWO. _x000D_ Apart from that, FWO itself also puts in place OS policy and has dedicated staff to follow up on that policy goal.

Audience or target group

Website

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Additional Activity Number

7.4

Additional Activity Name

Building industry-academia cooperation

Additional Activity type

7.4 Building industry-academia cooperation (e.g. GAIA-X and other industry-driven initiatives)

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Collaboration with national RPOs and researcher networks
2. Support the publication in Open Science Journals through internal grants
3. Fostering best practices in open science across researchers
4. Dedicated staff to support researchers with interdisciplinary data interoperability across department and projects
5. Establishment of Digital Competence Centers with a focus on improving research data management practises and the adoption of FAIR and Open Science
6. Engagement in several working groups and workshops, e.g., on metrics, architecture, metadata standards
7. Facilitation of dialog across research domains with relevant stakeholders
8. Support all research teams covering the entire data cycle, from writing DMPs, adopting appropriate storage solutions, depositing their datasets in open repositories
9. Communication and dissemination activities towards engagement of research communities in open science practice
10. Collection of regional competences and knowledge and make them available for industry
11. Organisation of a multi-disciplinary, annual scientific and technical users' conferences
12. The cost of personnel in Research Data/ Research Data Management Offices
13. The cost of personnel (developers, system managers, data curators) involved in local research infrastructure work

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

4 813 549 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

7.4

Success Story Name

Ecosystem of Excellence - University of Zagreb Computing Centre

Success story description

In 2022, SRCE participated in the creation of the EDIH proposal for CROatian Industry and Society BOosting (EDIH CROBOHUB++) project, which started on 1st January 2023. CROBOHUB ++ a is an ecosystem of excellence, specialized in three key areas of the Digital European Program (DEP): 1. Artificial intelligence, 2. Cybersecurity, 3. High-performance computing (HPC). It will form the core of a coherent package of services that will support SMEs that intend to harness the digital and green transformation in the EU.

Audience or target group

Website

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Additional Activity Number

Additional Activity Name

7.5

Enforcement and implementation of the EOSC Persistent Identifier (PID) policy and architecture

Additional Activity type

7.5 Enforcement and implementation of the EOSC Persistent Identifier (PID) policy and architecture

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Internal campaign for adoption and promotion of ORCID among staff and researchers from the linked organisations
2. PID analysis project within Knowledge Exchange Centre
3. Revision of institutional policies and enforcement of PIDs for all data holdings
4. The programme that aims to facilitate the production, access, sharing and management of information on national scientific activity
5. Implementation & maintenance of pilot PID services for national User community

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
 GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
 SO2 Professional data stewards are increasingly available in research performing organisations in Europe to support Open Science
 SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
 OO11 Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

356 454 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

7.5

Success Story Name

Integrated ecosystem - Foundation for Science and Technology

Success story description

This caption includes the effort to ensure compliance with the PTCRIS programme. This programme aims to facilitate the production, access, sharing and management of information on national scientific activity. It is responsible for developing a regulatory framework and infrastructures to create an integrated ecosystem of information on science in Portugal.

Audience or target group

Website

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Additional Activity Number

Additional Activity Name

7.6

Encouraging and incentivising use of European infrastructure for sharing of research software

Additional Activity type

7.6 Encouraging and incentivising use of European infrastructure for sharing of research software

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Encouraging use of image data tools developed in EOSC-Life
2. Internal campaign, using institutional newsletter, for promotion of EOSC membership and raise awareness of the importance of open standards and sharing of research software
3. FAIR software project within Knowledge Exchange Centre
4. Establishment and expansion of a software quality platform (EURISE Network) and bilateral collaborations with other scientific domains
5. Contribution to the European Software Sustainability Initiative (EUSI), the Workshops on Sustainable Software Sustainability (WOSSS) and the FAIR Software Route
6. HPCQS platform design activities
7. MeHeart open-source optimized model of solid mechanics of the myocardium to reproduce the cardiac electro-mechanics in HPC environment for industrial, clinical, and academic applications
8. Implementation of software metadata standards on DIGITAL.CSIC institutional repository to increase software visibility and metadata quality

Link to partnership general objectives

GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO6 Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
SO7 EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
OO1 Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
OO7 Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan- European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

266 020 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

7.6

Success Story Name

Platform design - Barcelona Supercomputing Center - Centro Nacional de Supercomputación

Success story description

HPCQS platform design (co-financed, <https://www.hpcqs.eu/>) activities. _x000D_ eFlows4HPC: Enabling dynamic and Intelligent workflows in the future EuroHPC ecosystem (co-financed, [https://www.bsc.es/research-and-development/projects/meheart-modelo-virtual-computacional-mecano-el%C3%A9ctrico-de-coraz%C3%B3n](https://www.bsc.es/research-and-development/projects/eflows4hpc-enabling-dynamic-and-intelligent-workflows-the-future)_x000D_ EarthSystemGrid Federation contribution, and Earth System Services. _x000D_ MeHeart open-source optimized model of solid mechanics of the myocardium to reproduce the cardiac electro-mechanics in HPC environment for industrial, clinical, and academic applications (<a href=))

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://www.bsc.es/research-and-development/projects/meheart-modelo-virtual-computacional-mecano-el%C3%A9ctrico-de-coraz%C3%B3n>

Additional Activity Number

7.7

Additional Activity Name

Monitoring of EOSC key performance indicators (KPI's), investments and FAIR data production and management

Additional Activity type

7.7 Monitoring of EOSC key performance indicators (KPI's), investments and FAIR data production and management

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Monitor institutional progress of KPIs by Open Science teams
2. Engagement in in OpenAIRE monitoring activities
3. Reporting activities and participation in WG KPIs and WG Landscape Analysis of national EOSC Mandated Organisation
4. Collection of KPIs based on ESFRI KPI framework
5. Contribution to national open science website by publishing an online open science dashboard with a variety of indicators
6. Performance of a national survey on the status of open access to research data
7. Involvement in activities relating to monitoring in the EOSC Steering Board and in the EOSC Association

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO5 The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
OO2 Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)
OO7 Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan- European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

170 333 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

7.7

Success Story Name

National Platform for Open Science - Data Archiving and Networked Services - Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW)

Success story description

DANS performs the Dutch National Open Science Desk (NOAD) function, participates in the National Platform for Open Science, contributes to the Dutch open science website and publishes an online open science dashboard with a variety of indicators. _x000D_ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/data-expertise/monitoring-and-analysis/>

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://dans.knaw.nl/en/data-expertise/monitoring-and-analysis/>

Additional Activity Number

7.8

Additional Activity Name

Contributing to a rewards and recognition framework that incentivises FAIR data and Open Science

Additional Activity type

7.8 Contributing to a rewards and recognition framework that incentivises FAIR data and Open Science

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Contribution to the alignment of the national rewards and incentives framework to the European initiatives
2. Participation in EOSC-A Advisory Group 'Research careers and curricula' – Task Force 'Research careers, recognition and credit'
3. Contributions to committees (e.g., EOSC TF Research careers and recognition and credit, The Guild) and contributions to institutional / national discussions
4. Creation of two new awards available to researchers: one for the 'best open access publication' and the other for the 'best FAIR research database'
5. Involvement in European initiatives such as the development of an agreement on Reforming Research Assessment
6. Ongoing support for the new evaluation system for university's professors
7. Scientometric analyses and advisory services for university's researchers and research units
8. A pilot for responsible metrics implementation in assessments and job applications
9. Development of national rewards and recognition framework within national FAIR Strategy implementation
10. Implementation of open science as part of assessment criteria for grant applications in 2022

- 11. Include the Open Science metrics, esp. data sharing, into the carrier reward system
- 12. Establishment of Research Assessment group
- 13. Participation in initiatives outside EOSC Association (e.g. in cOAlition S and Science Europe)
- 14. Establishment of internal working groups dedicated to rewards and recognitions as well as research assessment

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
 GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
 SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
 OO8 Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

- Yes
- No

Funding sources

- Public
- Private

Amount per activity

3 910 216 €

Success story

- Yes
- No

Success story number

7.8

Success Story Name

Coordination - OpenAIRE

Success story description

Inform and coordinate through our Open Science Strategy (internal) Standing Committee our members on the latest developments. Participate in all European fora on the topic. Contribute towards new metrics via services based on the OpenAIRE Research Graph.

Audience or target group

- Industry
- Research Institutes
- Academia
- Public Authorities
- Public at large
- Other

Website

Additional Activity Number

7.9

Additional Activity Name

Activities contributing to strategic and operational alignment, coordination and synergies with other partnerships, HE missions, initiatives, research data commons and data spaces

Additional Activity type

7.9 Activities contributing to strategic and operational alignment, coordination and synergies with other partnerships, HE missions, initiatives, research data commons and data spaces

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Collaboration with other infrastructures, partnerships, Horizon Europe mission, to implement into the strategic and operational plans at EU level innovative paediatric research to be developed in synergy.
2. Establishment of national Open Science Task Forces and/ or national EOSC Support Offices
3. Coordination of national Open Science Cloud Initiative as national, organizational, and technological environment which encourages and enables open science by providing the resources and services needed for collecting, processing, storing, sharing, and reusing research data following FAIR principles.
4. Participation in Executive Board in Competence Centers
5. Participation in national Open Science Observatories
6. Participation in EOSC task forces UNIBO, in Open Science working groups of The Guild
7. Coordination of national Network for e-Science, fostering the cooperation among main national stakeholders in e-Science, including Open Science
8. Contribution to national Open Research Forum which brings together stakeholders in national research ecosystem to help develop national policies on open research
9. Stakeholder-Management and Communication with Connectome Research Infrastructure Partners and prospective Partners, EOSC national group alignment
10. Collaboration with other important institution and initiatives contributing to strategic and operational alignment: Science Europe, part of CoNOSC, acting as national RDA Node
11. Connection to the European Consortia of Universities for practices exchange and a correlation of OS approaches
12. Contributions to discussions in committees (e.g., The Guild, EUA, LIBER, RDA)
13. Alignment with euroCRIS and EOSC

14. Coordination of national network and programs on RDM policies to support information exchange and to create and pilot new RDM services
15. Alignment between various national universities and with national administration
16. Cooperation between universities and national funding organisations to establish an interaction between research information systems and research data management infrastructures with the aid of digital technologies
17. Development of common definition of components of the national infrastructure for 1 million genomes (part of the Health Data Space) with relevant stakeholders
18. Collaboration with main national providers of data services to have a better integrated national data infrastructure in place
19. Contribution to the National e-Science Network
20. Coordination of National Institute of Bioinformatic
21. Participation to National Open Science Committee, and national EOSC working groups
22. Contribution to relevant EU initiatives aligned with EOSC objectives: SeaDATANET, Science Europe, GBIF, OPERAS
23. Participation in the community of IODE Ocean Best Practices system and in the Inter-sessional Working Group to propose a Strategy on Ocean Data and Information Stewardship for the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development 2021-2030

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
 GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
 SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
 SO9 EOSC increasingly establishes ties with related initiatives from regions around the world and becomes a partner in global cooperation frameworks for Open Science
 OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

15 568 583 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

7.9

Success Story Name

Strategic and operational alignment - Unitatea Executiva pentru Finantarea / Invatamantul Superior, a Cercetarii, Dezvoltarii si Inovarii

Success story description

Collaboration with other important institution and initiatives contributing to strategic and operational alignment: Science Europe (SE Working Group on Open Science) Part of CoNOSC. Connection to the European Consortia of Universities (e.g. CIVIS, CIVITAS) for practices exchange and a correlation of OS approaches. Acting as the RDA Node Romania.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

Additional Activity Number

7.11

Additional Activity Name

Contact points at national or institutional levels and coordination mechanisms for EOSC uptake by the research communities, infrastructure connection and FAIR implementation

Additional Activity type

7.10 Contact points at national or institutional levels and coordination mechanisms for EOSC uptake by the research communities, infrastructure connection and FAIR implementation

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Participation in the Hellenic Open Science Initiative, which aims to promote EOSC in the country
2. Operation of contact points concerning EOSC activities, related projects, RDM steering group, research data networks

3. Coordination activities for National Open Science Cloud Initiative
4. Coordination of OS activities relevant at national level and acts as an OS and EOSC helpdesk, supporting the EOSC uptake, being connected to the main initiatives
5. Coordination of the national EOSC Forum, running EOSC national Coordination Forum
6. Coordination of the national OS Taskforce, engagement with national stakeholders, co-creation activities for potential 'EOSC-proof' services in collaboration with research organisations and researchers
7. ERIC contact point that coordinates mechanisms for EOSC uptake at national or institutional level (i.e., raising awareness, onboard services on the EOSC Marketplace)
8. Contact point for EOSC for national Association of Higher Educational Institutions
9. Design of governance model to engage stakeholders ("mirroring the EOSC Association activities") in the national EOSC building activities
10. Coordination of activities and information flows, liaising with the involved ministries and national funding agencies
11. Financial support for EOSC Membership for national institutions
12. Contact point for Service Providers in member countries
13. Staff dedicated to disseminating information among members, and strengthening reinforcement of cooperation to EOSC from all the HE institutions
14. Coordination of national activities towards the implementation of EOSC, including work on the general conditions for this implementation participation in the coordination board for implementation of the EOSC initiative on a national level
15. Coordinating of works of the national members of EOSC Association, as well as liaising with those institutions that consider joining the EOSC Association
16. Provision of a communication platform for the institutions, which are not members of the EOSC Association, but whose Open Science initiatives and investments can be aligned with EOSC

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research

SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science

SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)

OO2 Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)

OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

Yes

No

Funding sources

Public

Private

Amount per activity

5 488 171 €

Success story

Yes

No

Success story number

7.1

Success Story Name

Coordinating national activities - Masaryk University

Success story description

Coordinating national activities towards the implementation of EOSC, preparing the strategic systematic project EOSC-CZ (launched on 1st of January 2023, under MU coordination). This included close collaboration with the relevant Ministry and their strategic board on the definition of the general conditions for and scope of the strategic intervention for the EOSC implementation in Czechia.

Audience or target group

- Industry
 Research Institutes
 Public at large
- Academia
 Public Authorities
 Other

Website

Additional Activity category

8. Communication, dissemination, awareness raising, citizen engagement

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category includes activities in the areas of communication and dissemination, in order to ensure that citizens "take up" and accept the new product/innovation, as well as learning about user needs. It also goes further to cover activities that aim at awareness raising and stakeholder engagement in relation to the new product/innovation.

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
 No

Amount per category

6 474 084 €

Additional Activity Number	Additional Activity Name
8.1	EOSC-related communication, dissemination, outreach and awareness raising activities

Additional Activity type

8.1 EOSC-related communication, dissemination, outreach and awareness raising activities

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. EOSC-related communication and awareness raising activities, using all available communication institutional channels, including webpages, magazines, newsletters and through social networks
2. Dissemination, outreach, social media postings, events and webinars targeted widely for research communities on topics including research data management, EOSC, EUDAT, FAIR data, data infrastructures and research data services
3. Dissemination actions with respect to EOSC during national e-Science meetings
4. PR activities with national press and magazines (scientific, IT related, broad coverage, ...)
5. Awareness raising activities in diverse contexts (e.g., institutional meetings and events, university alliances)
6. Creation of a dedicated space on the institutional website to explain EOSC, publicize our membership and gather attention from our community
7. Local and national workshops and events
8. Dissemination of EOSC policy, funding, and other activities from the European to national and local level
9. Roadshow and promoting EOSC to research communities
10. Update of engagement strategy
11. Activities of communication and awareness of the Scientific Culture
12. Dissemination activities related to EOSC near the community, namely through the RDM Forum event
13. Online materials devoted to EOSC and Open Science that will be disseminated among national researchers, data stewards, service providers, university authorities as well as local and national authorities
14. Creating, transferring, and promoting informational and promotional content via the website, social media, as well as events and publications
15. Digital University Hub is the cooperation and service platform for digital and social transformation initiatives by Austrian universities
16. Conferences, articles, publications, online events (e.g., the "Open Science Café)
17. Organization of promotion and outreach activities updating the information on the website on mapping of research infrastructures
18. Development of and contribution to guidelines related to European policy framework and EOSC

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO2 Professional data stewards are increasingly available in research performing organisations in Europe to support Open Science
SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
OO3 Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership
OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

5 488 171 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

8.1

Success Story Name

Outreach - EUDAT LTD

Success story description

Dissemination, outreach, social media postings, events and webinars targeted widely for research communities on topics including research data management, EOSC, EUDAT, FAIR data, data infrastructures and research data services.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

Additional Activity Number

8.2

Additional Activity Name

Promoting EOSC at all levels by engaging with relevant communities and stakeholders

Additional Activity type

8.2 Promoting EOSC at all levels by engaging with relevant communities and stakeholders

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Maintenance of dedicated webpage on EOSC-related activities, addressed to various communities
2. Engagement activities through EOSC Board and membership fee
3. Regular webinars with researchers where EOSC and engagement opportunities are disseminated
4. Management of large platforms such as BrainMap - the online community of researchers, innovators, technicians, and entrepreneurs with more than 42.000 accounts or EERIS platform that offers an overview of existing research facilities, equipment, services, and technological services at national level
5. Promotion of EOSC in various activities, sometimes in cooperation with OpenAIRE
6. Promotion of the federation of existing services and data at the European level
7. Promotion of EOSC policy, funding, and other activities from the European to national and local level
8. Leverage of existing network and communication channels to general e-infrastructure users' community
9. Promotion of EOSC by engaging with research communities in the SSH
10. Interactive webinars and EOSC conversations
11. Promotion of Open Science with national events, press releases, posts on social media, web news on institutional web sites, paper material (leaflets, roll up, posters), contents on the dedicated section of the institutional web portal
12. Citizen engagement through monitoring surveys with the use of innovative applications
13. Collaboration with funders, research organizations, policymakers, and research communities

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
SO9 EOSC increasingly establishes ties with related initiatives from regions around the world and becomes a partner in global cooperation frameworks for Open Science
OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
OO5 Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
OO7 Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan- European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025
OO8 Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership
OO9 Implement and evolve the EOSC Rules of Participation and onboarding process for EOSC providers and increase the number of service providers and services offered progressively over the course of the Partnership
OO14 Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

3 442 347 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

8.2

Success Story Name

National/International platforms - Unitatea Executiva pentru Finantarea / Invatamantului Superior, a Cercetarii, Dezvoltarii si Inovarii

Success story description

UEFISCDI is managing large platforms such as BrainMap (<https://www.brainmap.ro>) - the online community of researchers, innovators, technicians and entrepreneurs with more than 42.000 accounts or EERIS platform (Engage in the European Research Infrastructures System Platform, <https://eeris.eu/>) that offers an overview of existing research facilities, equipment, services and technological services at national level, and it is currently running a series of pilot activities with other European countries, in order to expand EERIS internationally.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://eeris.eu>

Additional Activity category

9. Other

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category includes any other activities that cannot be included in the above categories

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
 No

Amount per category

15 568 583 €

Additional Activity Number

9.1

Additional Activity Name

Introduction of EOSC-specific references in research programmes and EOSC-related criteria for R&I funding

Additional Activity type

9.1 Introduction of EOSC-specific references in research programmes and EOSC-related criteria for R&I funding

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

- 1.Elaboration of a concrete roadmap/ action plan with indicators corelated to the EU policy recommendations and correlated with SRIA and the EOSC Partnership KPIs, including proposals/ estimates of the financial interventions needed at national level
- 2.Support in drafting OS related criteria in different funding streams
- 3.Contribution to the Horizon Europe Programme (HE) in collaboration with the national HE Programme Committee Research Infrastructures
- 4.Support researchers in integrating EOSC & FAIR in proposals, support researchers to comply with requirements for projects
- 5.University policy for Open Science and Open Access, finalization, and implementation

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

15 000 €

Success story

- Yes

No

Additional Activity Number

9.2

Additional Activity Name

Activities in support of open publishing and initiatives to promote wider open access publication through the EOSC

Additional Activity type

9.2 Activities in support of open publishing and initiatives to promote wider open access publication through the EOSC

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

1. Development, support, and promotion of the national infrastructure for OA and activities on boarding those infrastructures to EOSC
2. Enforcement of the open access policy for mandatory deposit of publications and data in the institutional repositories - OpenAIRE compliant - through the recruitment of new library staff for full-text check
3. Support to diamond open access through the institutional e-publishing platforms for open access peer-reviewed journals and books
4. Institutional contributions to European infrastructures (e.g., OPERAS, OpenAIRE)
5. Liaison activities with Open Research Europe - ORE and Open Repositories at EU, national and regional levels
6. Collaboration with other organisations, support Open Science organisations like SCOSS, participation in OpenAIRE
7. Open Access initiatives for digital publications
8. Involvement in the international coalition, cOAlition S, which is behind Plan S
9. Operation of the institutional open access repository Research Collection
10. Support open access data journal Research Data Journal for Social Sciences and Humanities
11. Support for researchers with finding appropriate research repositories and support in the deposition process
12. Operation of institutional DSpace repository
13. Development of guides for open access publishing in Horizon Europe
14. Provision of technical links from OpenAIRE repositories to Open Research Europe
15. CzechElib - transition to Gold OA via transformative agreements, National repository, Implementation of European OS standards

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
- SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
- SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
- OO1 Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
- OO3 Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

5 206 455 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

9.2

Success Story Name

Publishing Initiatives - Alma MaTTER

Success story description

1. Transformative "Publish and Read agreements" with the main international publishers and APCs monitoring
x000D _x000D_ 2. Enforcement of the open access policy for mandatory deposit of publications and data in the institutional repositories - OpenAIRE compliant - through the recruitment of new library staff for full-text check
x000D _x000D_ 3. Support to diamond open access through the institutional e-publishing platforms for open access peer-reviewed journals and books. The reduction in the contribution is essentially due to two factors: - staff that we had planned to report but were paid with funds that were indirectly attributable to European funding. The University of Bologna and the Research Centre for Open Scholarly Metadata manage OpenCitations infrastructure, an independent not-for-profit organization for open scholarship dedicated to the publication of open bibliographic and citation data by the use of Semantic Web technologies. The reduction in the contribution is essentially due to two factors: - staff that we had planned to report but were paid with funds that were indirectly attributable to European funding. In 2021 the University of Bologna started the up-grade of ACNP, the Italian union catalogue of serials, which

includes data about 258,221 serials held in 1937 academic and research libraries. The catalogue wishes to enhance its records with information about Open Access, including data from ROAD (the Directory of Open Access scholarly Resources) and DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals). The catalogue will offer information about policies for OA, licenses, publication fees and conditions offered by the different institutions part of the catalogue. ACNP will also evaluate the provision of links about data repository facilities for journals in the catalogue.

Audience or target group

Website

- Industry
- Academia
- Research Institutes
- Public Authorities
- Public at large
- Other

Additional Activity Number

Additional Activity Name

9.3

Adoption of national or institutional strategies for digital transformation and related roadmaps including a reference to the EOSC

Additional Activity type

9.3 Adoption of national or institutional strategies for digital transformation and related roadmaps including a reference to the EOSC

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

- 1.Support to the implementation of the Digital Bible priorities
- 2.Digitisation projects of cultural heritage collections within the national program of the Ministry of Culture
- 3.Research Data Management policy
- 4.Adoption of national strategies, e.g. National Strategy Open Research Data
- 5.Development of national roadmap on Open Science
- 6.Participation in projects aligned with the National AI strategy and actions in the field of data platforms
- 7.Promotion of digital enabling technologies such as connectivity infrastructures or massive data environments to facilitate data sharing
- 8.Development of advanced data management and analysis capabilities linked to strategic Supercomputing infrastructures (HPC)
- 9.Finalization of the university roadmap on open science, essentially on open data
- 10.Adoption and implementation of Institutional Strategies on Open Science
- 11.Implementation of national digital transformation strategies through the University Action Plan
- 12.Contribution to the National Roadmap for Digital Transformation which also included actions for Open Science and EOSC
- 13.Implementation of the institutional strategies for digital transformation and related roadmaps through a dedicated working group, periodical meetings, and the involvement of all institute's personnel

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
- GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
- SO2 Professional data stewards are increasingly available in research performing organisations in Europe to support Open Science
- SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
- SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
- SO9 EOSC increasingly establishes ties with related initiatives from regions around the world and becomes a partner in global cooperation frameworks for Open Science
- OO1 Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
- OO2 Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)
- OO3 Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO6 Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO8 Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO13 Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users

Link to projects

- Yes
- No

Funding sources

- Public
-

Amount per activity

1 780 278 €

Private

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

9.3

Success Story Name

National Roadmap - National Infrastructures for Research and Technology - GRNET S.A.

Success story description

GRNET contributed in the National Roadmap for Digital Transformation which included also actions for Open Science and EOSC https://digitalstrategy.gov.gr/website/static/website/assets/uploads/digital_strategy.pdf and is actively developing a number of actions. Due to the constraints of the timeframe to submit this survey we are unable to offer an estimation of the effort allocated to that. Thus we report only the effort to contribute in writing this Roadmap.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

https://digitalstrategy.gov.gr/website/static/website/assets/uploads/digital_strategy

Additional Activity Number

9.4

Additional Activity Name

Adoption of new policies on Open Science referring to the use of the EOSC or the implementation of the FAIR principles.

Additional Activity type

9.4 Adoption of new policies on Open Science referring to the use of the EOSC or the implementation of the FAIR principles. Definition of policy targets and action plans for the implementation of those policies

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

- 1.Support the implementation of activities included in the proposal for a National Open Science Plan
- 2.Plan S implementation, national Open Science Board roadmap implementation
- 3.Completion of national policies on Open Science
- 4.Ensure a long-term connection to the major EU initiatives and the national ones
- 5.Operation of NOSCI forum
- 6.Contribution to the development of national policies, agenda, objectives on OS in the OS national Taskforce
- 7.Adoption of national roadmap on Open Science
- 8.Develop an update of the open science and the publication policy
- 9.Implementation of institutional RDM/ OS policy
- 10.Development of the concept of a national strategic document on Open Science for the Ministry of Education and Research
- 11.Development of national and institutional strategic document templates on Open Access, Open Science (for research performing and research funding organizations)
- 12.Development of the Institutional Open Research Data Policy framework
- 13.Development and implementation of national policies on Open Science
- 14.Revision of policies to adhere to new national ORD strategy, which also refers to EOSC
- 15.Implementation of institutional policy on FAIR Data & software
- 16.Development of a set of recommendations in relation to infrastructure and various research artefacts (research publications, data, software, open-source code) at national and institutional level
- 17.Continuation and enforcement of the institutional mandate for Open Access publications through DIGITAL repository

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

2 355 500 €

Success

story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

9.4

Success Story Name

National Policies - Institute for Development of Information Society (Moldova)

Success story description

Developing the concept of a national strategic document on Open Science for the Ministry of Education and Research _x000D_ Development of national and institutional strategic document templates on Open Access, Open Science (for research performing and research funding organizations) _x000D_ Development of the Institutional Open Research Data Policy framework

Audience or target group

Website

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Additional Activity Number

9.5

Additional Activity Name

Liaise internationally to develop a global cooperation framework for Open Science infrastructures

Additional Activity type

9.5 Liaise internationally to develop a global cooperation framework for Open Science infrastructures

Description of Additional Activity

This Additional Activities' type includes as follows:

- 1.Collaboration aimed at increasing the awareness for the potential benefits of sharing language resource enabled by the interoperability framework
- 2.Maintenance of existing links with active consortia in South Africa, the US, Australia, and Latin America
- 3.Organization of promotion and outreach activities updating the information on the website on mapping of research infrastructures
- 4.Active liaisons with regional networks around the world (Canada, Latin America, UN, GOSC, RDA, COAR) which include technology transfer, know-how and practices

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
SO9 EOSC increasingly establishes ties with related initiatives from regions around the world and becomes a partner in global cooperation frameworks for Open Science

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

6 211 350 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

9.5

Success Story Name

SARS-CoV-2 - Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information

Success story description

Provision of technical and personnel capacities for SARS-CoV-2 sequences processing in Slovakia. _x000D_ Data upload in the required standards to GISAID and ENA (European Nucleotide Archive) and to covid19dataportal.org. Bioinformatics services provided by the Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information for sequencing laboratories - raw data supplied by laboratories are then processed into the required form. If required, it is possible to create exports and various visualizations from these systems nationally and

internationally.

Audience or target group

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industry | <input type="checkbox"/> Academia |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research Institutes | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public Authorities |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Public at large | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |

Website

<https://otvorenaveda.cvtisr.sk/narodna-strategia-otvorenej-vedy>